

Instructions for Paper Submissions to PPSN 2026: Supplementary Materials

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1 Dataset and experiments setting

1.1 Dataset

The stock price dataset covers market trading records from December 20, 1990, to December 10, 2015, comprising a total of 6,090 observations. Each data record consists of five core fields. Date: A timestamp indicating the trading day; Open: The initial trading price at the opening of the securities market on that day; Close: The final transaction price at the end of the trading day; Low: The lowest price point within the day’s price fluctuation range; High: The peak price reached during the trading session.

The Beijing PM2.5 monitoring dataset, sourced from the UC Irvine Machine Learning Repository, spans five years of observations from January 2010 to December 2014, comprising a total of 43,824 samples. Each sample consists of eight air quality parameters. Date: Date and time of the observation; PM2.5: Concentration of PM2.5 particulate matter; DEWP: Dew point temperature, the critical temperature at which air becomes saturated with water vapor; TEMP: Ambient temperature; PRES: Atmospheric pressure; cbwd: Combined wind direction indicator; Iws: Cumulative wind speed; Is: Accumulated snow thickness; Ir: Precipitation index. Among these, the PM2.5 concentration serves as the primary observation metric, reflecting the real-time pollution level of fine particulate matter in the air. The remaining meteorological parameters provide multidimensional auxiliary data to support environmental factor analysis.

The NOx emission dataset from production monitoring records of a petrochemical refinery originates from actual production data recorded at the Fluid Catalytic Cracking Unit of a Chinese petrochemical refinery. The data spans from March 1, 2016, to February 1, 2017, with a recording interval of 40 minutes. After data cleaning, over 10,000 records were obtained. The specific indicators include four production factors. Feedstock Flow Rate unit: (m^3/h); Coke Burner Temperature (unit: $^{\circ}C$); Main Air Flow Rate (unit: kNm^3/h); Flue Gas Temperature (unit: $^{\circ}C$); along with NOx Emission Concentration (unit: mg/m^3).

The NOx concentration data were collected by sensors with precisions of 0.001 and 0.15, respectively.

This experiment employs a training-test split strategy with a ratio of 7:3. The task is formulated as one-step-ahead forecasting, where the model predicts y_{t+1} from an input window of length $L = 8$. And the results of each experiment are averaged over 10 runs with different random seeds. Regarding the prediction task settings, each dataset corresponds to distinct research objectives: the stock price dataset targets the daily highest trading price (High) for modeling, the Beijing PM2.5 dataset focuses on monitoring PM2.5 particulate matter concentration, and the NOx emission dataset aims to predict NOx emission levels. For multivariate datasets, all variables are treated as independent input channels, and their temporal relationships are learned directly by the RNN. As illustrated in (Figure. 1), the visualization clearly delineates the dataset division boundaries with a red demarcation line, where the left region represents training samples and the right region represents validation samples.

Fig. 1. The evolution of prediction targets in the experiments (a) Stock Price Dataset, (b) Beijing PM2.5 Dataset, (c) NOx Emission Dataset.

The multidimensional datasets involved in this study exhibit significant differences in magnitude, which can easily lead to parameter weight imbalances during the training of machine learning models. In deep neural networks, features with dominant magnitudes tend to dictate the direction of gradient updates, resulting in model convergence bias. This study employs the Min-Max Scaling method, which consists of two core steps: first, the raw data are calibrated against the minimum value; then, a linear mapping function is constructed by calculating the feature range (the difference between the maximum and minimum values) to compress each dimension of the data into the closed interval $[0, 1]$. The mathematical expression for this standardization process is given by:

$$x' = \frac{x - x_{\min}}{x_{\max} - x_{\min}} \quad (1)$$

where x represents the raw data, and x_{\min} and x_{\max} denote the minimum and maximum values in the dataset, respectively.

This linear transformation method effectively eliminates the interference caused by magnitude differences in model training, ensuring that each feature contributes comparably to the neural network. Compared to Z-Score Scaling, Min-Max Scaling is particularly suitable for scenarios with well-defined data distribution boundaries.

1.2 Experiments setting

To ensure the reproducibility of experimental results, this study employs a rigorous control variable approach by setting a fixed random seed to initialize parameter states. The reported results are the average outcomes of 10 runs with different fixed random seeds. The weight initialization strategy follows $\theta_0 \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.001^2 I_d)$, with the constraint $|\theta_0^{(i)}| \leq 0.03$, to prevent saturation of the activation function.

The RNN model is structured with an input layer in \mathbb{R}^n (using the "High" feature for the stock price dataset and "pm2.5, DEWP, TEMP, PRES, cbwd, lws" for the Beijing PM2.5 dataset), a hidden layer in \mathbb{R}^{64} , and an output layer in \mathbb{R}^1 , utilizing the Tanh activation function for nonlinear feature mapping. The LSTM model has an input layer in \mathbb{R}^n , a hidden layer in \mathbb{R}^{64} , an output layer in \mathbb{R}^1 , and a time step of 8. The mean squared error (MSE) is used as the loss function.

The BPTT and RNN-PF methods differ in their optimization strategies and hyperparameter configurations, but share common parameters: the loss function is MSE, the maximum training epochs are $E_{\max} = 30$, and the batch size is $B = 16$. For BPTT, the Adam optimizer is used with a learning rate of $\eta = 0.01$. For the RNN-PF method, the decay strategy and relaxation mechanism functions for the two types of covariance matrices involve two hyperparameters. Through a simple grid search, the reference range for the hyperparameter α was determined to be approximately $[1.2, 1.8]$, while the hyperparameter β was found to be around 0.6. Testing revealed that the experimental results are relatively insensitive to these hyperparameters, exhibiting a large tolerance range. In all experimental datasets, the configurations were set as $\alpha = 1.5$, $\beta = 0.6$, $\sigma_{\max} = 0.5$, and $\rho_{\max} = 0.5$.

Regarding the particle number configuration, the algorithm's time complexity is $O(n)$ with respect to the number of particles n . As shown in Figure. 2, the runtime curve indicates that as the number of particles increases, the training time required to complete a fixed number of iterations also rises. The loss curve demonstrates that after completing the 30th epoch, the model's prediction accuracy on the training set, based on the weights, initially decreases and then increases. For $n > 60$, as the number of particles grows, the training accuracy exhibits a slight decline. Analysis reveals that a certain number of particles can sufficiently ensure effective convergence of the particle ensemble toward the optimal parameter θ^* . However, excessively broad sampling causes particle motion during training to favor diffusive behavior over localized fine-grained search, which is detrimental to improving training accuracy. Therefore, considering both dimensions, the particle number hyperparameter is configured as $n = 2^6$. In the experiments with the NOx emission dataset, apply the reformulated relaxation mechanism with $\zeta = 0.006$.

Fig. 2. The impact of different particle numbers on training accuracy and training efficiency.

2 More result analysis

Figure. 3, Figure.4, and Table 1 collectively present the performance on the Beijing PM2.5 dataset. The RNN-PF training method demonstrates algorithmic advantages on the Beijing PM2.5 dataset that are nearly consistent with those observed on the stock price dataset. The final training loss MAE of RNN-PF (15.9093) is 5.3% lower than that of RNN-BPTT (16.7881) and 3.9% lower than that of LSTM-BPTT (16.5581), validating the adaptability of the particle filtering mechanism to non-stationary time series. On the test set, RNN-PF’s MAE (14.9178) is 5.1% lower than that of LSTM-BPTT (15.7202), and its R^2 value (0.9320) improves by 2.0%.

Table 1. Comparison of evaluation metrics for model’s prediction results at the end of training on the Beijing PM2.5 train dataset and test dataset.

Method	MAE	RMSE	R2
RNN-BPTT	16.7881	27.7374	0.9081
LSTM-BPTT	16.5581	29.7855	0.894
RNN-PF	15.9093±0.4774	26.0881±0.1708	0.9187±0.0011

Method	MAE	RMSE	R2
RNN-BPTT	16.022	24.8974	0.9227
LSTM-BPTT	15.7202	26.3044	0.9137
RNN-PF	14.9187±0.3159	23.2615±0.1897	0.9320±0.0011

Fig. 3. Training loss dynamics on the Beijing PM2.5 dataset.

Fig. 4. Comparison of model's prediction results on the Beijing PM2.5 test dataset.

3 Methodological Clarifications and Extended Discussions

This section provides extended discussions and methodological clarifications regarding sensitivity analysis and robustness of the proposed RNN-PF framework, incorporating evaluations to further validate the algorithm’s stability.

3.1 Handling of Noisy Data and Generalization

The model regulates its tolerance to observational noise through the observation likelihood covariance matrix. Particles that demonstrate greater consistency with the underlying data trend achieve higher likelihoods and are progressively reinforced over multiple iterations. In contrast, particles that overfit to noise fail to consistently attain high likelihoods across successive time steps and are gradually phased out. The adaptive observation covariance directly incorporates both the prediction error and label confidence. For instance, in the NOx dataset, the parameter ζ (confidence coefficient for training labels) is linked to sensor accuracy, thereby assigning physical interpretability to this hyperparameter. Higher sensor accuracy corresponds to a smaller ζ , leading the system to place greater trust in the corresponding labels.

While no explicit regularization is used, RNN-PF provides implicit regularization through particle posterior averaging, which suppresses noise-driven overfitting by assigning lower weights to overfitted particles. The persistent noise injection further offers a Dropout-like effect, and the error-adaptive covariance mechanism prevents premature particle collapse when overfitting is detected. Collectively, these mechanisms enable the system to automatically distinguish between signal and noise within a Bayesian framework.

3.2 State-Space Reformulation and Sensitivity Analysis

Regarding the spectral radius constraint, by setting an upper bound ρ_{\max} for the standard deviation of process noise, direct control over the diffusion range is achieved, equivalent to constraining the spectral radius of the covariance matrix. A direct theoretical guarantee for boundedness of particle evolution in high-dimensional nonlinear RNN parameter spaces is generally not available in the literature. Our mechanism is fundamentally an empirically derived stabilization strategy rather than a theoretically proven convergence guarantee.

To thoroughly evaluate the sensitivity of the approach, we assessed the effect of the initialization standard deviation over $\text{std} \in \{0.005, 0.01, 0.02, 0.05\}$. As shown in Table 2, for $\text{std} = 0.005$ to 0.02 , the model remains highly stable with minimal variance across runs, indicating that performance is essentially insensitive within this range. When the standard deviation increases to 0.05 , the RMSE rises significantly. RNN-PF is robust to moderate initialization noise, but exhibits a distinct degradation once initialization induces excessively dispersed initial particles. The sensitivity boundary is therefore localized around $\text{std} \approx 0.02 - 0.05$.

Table 2. Sensitivity analysis of the initialization standard deviation on model performance.

Init std	Test MAE	Test RMSE	Test R ²
0.005	34.0693 ± 1.0211	50.7690 ± 1.0952	0.9927 ± 0.0003
0.01	34.0500 ± 0.7930	50.2987 ± 0.9059	0.9928 ± 0.0003
0.02	35.6583 ± 1.0578	52.5593 ± 1.1183	0.9922 ± 0.0003
0.05	46.7049 ± 3.5677	64.7868 ± 4.2052	0.9881 ± 0.0015

Furthermore, to assess the robustness of the proposed adaptive covariance decay mechanism, we conducted a grid search over the decay step size $\eta \in \{0.03, 0.05, 0.07\}$ and the decay exponent $\alpha \in \{1.0, 1.5, 2.0\}$. The results are presented in Table 3. It is evident that α is the dominant factor. When $\alpha = 1.0$ or 1.5, all η values produce stable, nearly identical performance. When $\alpha = 2.0$, performance deteriorates sharply, indicating high sensitivity when contraction is overly aggressive. η plays a secondary and mild role. Overall, sensitivity is highly anisotropic: performance is much more sensitive to α than to η . Stable regions are well-defined ($\eta \in [0.03, 0.07]$, $\alpha \in [1.0, 1.5]$), and particle collapse occurs only when α pushes variance contraction beyond a tolerable rate.

Table 3. Grid search results for the adaptive covariance decay mechanism parameters.

η	α	MAE	RMSE	R ²
0.03	1	33.2858	50.0347	0.9929
0.03	1.5	79.4717	105.5562	0.9683
0.03	2	527.4211	653.2092	-0.2127
0.05	1	35.1877	51.6117	0.9924
0.05	1.5	33.1147	49.1950	0.9931
0.05	2	266.9291	337.4420	0.6764
0.07	1	35.9888	51.6796	0.9924
0.07	1.5	33.5883	50.1857	0.9928
0.07	2	152.6780	199.0219	0.8874

3.3 Particle Degeneracy and Resampling Strategy

To mitigate particle degeneracy, the proposed method utilizes a weighted average over the particle posterior, which functionally corresponds to a deterministic form of systematic resampling. To quantitatively assess particle diversity, we monitored the normalized effective sample size (ESS) throughout training for both our strategy and standard SIR. The results are summarized in Table 4.

These results indicate that both methods effectively avoid particle degeneracy, with ESS maintaining levels far above conventional thresholds. Although

Table 4. Quantitative assessment of normalized effective sample size (ESS) over training.

Method	Min	Max	Average	Std
Our strategy	0.8817	0.9836	0.9731	0.0237
Standard SIR	0.9740	1.0000	0.9974	0.0046

standard SIR exhibits slightly higher ESS, our method maintains sufficient diversity without the need for explicit resampling operations. Overall, the ESS analysis confirms that the proposed update rule effectively preserves particle diversity over long sequential iterations.